

An Overview on usage of Artificial Intelligence in Banking Industry

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Abstract

Banking industry is the backbone of the whole economy. Banking definition reveals the main objective of banking industry that is acceptance of deposits and lending of loans to customers. According to world bank report, in India there are 3.5 ATM's and 7 branches for 1,00,000 people government aims to include maximum number of people under the banking umbrella and hence, the government has introduced Jandhan Yojana (zero balance account) type of financial inclusion schemes. Nowadays, banks apart from fulfilling their basic objective of acceptance of deposits and lending of loans, they are into providing certain value added services to the customers such as merchant banking, loan syndication, factoring, smart cards, micro finance, leasing, foreign exchange services, portfolio management and fund transferring services. Online banking system has turned as a boon to the banking industry, where latest technologies with Artificial Intelligence have been implemented successfully.” Artificial Intelligence is the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence “.

With the introduction of AI in banking sector risk assessment, financial analysis and portfolio management functions are becoming more effective. Chatbots, AML pattern detection techniques, Algorithmic trading, etc. type of technologies are being used in the above areas. This paper wants to reveal the areas where AI has been invested successfully and the future areas where it can be implemented.

Keywords: Jandhan Yojana (Zero Account Balance), Chat boats, Foreign Exchange, Merchant Banking, AML pattern detection.

Introduction

Banking industry is the backbone of the economy India's banking sector is on a high growth trend with around 3.5 and less than 7 bank branches per 10,00,000 people. According to the World Bank Report. Nowadays, banks apart from fulfilling their basic objective of acceptance of deposits and lending of loans, they are into providing certain value added services to the customer such as merchant banking, loan syndication, factoring, smart cards, leasing, foreign exchange services, portfolio management and fund transferring services. Online banking system has turned as a boon to the banking industry which has minimized the work of staff which is a valuable gift by digital technology. But when the risk factor is concerned people are

hesitating to use online banking system for varied services because of the risk of illegal entrants who tries to hack the precious data, mishandling of funds etc. According to a recent survey 88% of respondent's see AI as a foundational change for risk management. In India, banking sector is becoming one of the first adopters of AI. AI can give assistance in cash transfer, cards management and risk management through various tools like chatbots for customer services for individuals and even placing an AI robot for self service at banks. Even AI can support back office operations and can reduce inefficiency of employees and risks.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the present areas where AI has been implemented in banking sector.
- To know the future areas where AI can be implemented.

Methodology of Research

Whole study is based on empirical data. Information has been collected from secondary source such as journals, articles, blogs from internet.

Review of Literature

- Hamid Eslami Nosratabadi, Ahmad Nadali, and Sanaz pourdrab presented paper on “credit assessment of bank customers by a fuzzy expert system based on rules extracted from association rules”. That states credit assessment is a very typical classification problem in data mining.
- R.V Kulkarni, B.L Desai presented paper on “knowledge based system in banking sector”. Said that in view of enhanced competition, the banking sector has already taken Strides toward computerization and automate of their operations.

Definition

- Oxford Dictionary defines a bank as “an establishment for custody of money, which it pays out a customers order”.
- According to john McCarthy “intelligence is the computational part of the ability to achieve goals in the world”.

AI and its Relevance to Banking

Nowadays, technology itself is getting smarter day by day, allowing more and more newer inventions and innovations. For banking sector the application of AI is the most necessitated one. Banking sector is becoming first amongst other industries in implementing AI in its regular and day to day operations. And just like other segments, banks are exploring and implementing the technology in various ways.

1. AML (Anti-money laundering) Pattern Detection: Refers to a set of procedures, laws or regulations designed to stop the practice of generating income through illegal actions. Most of the major banks across the globe are shifting form rule based software system to AI based systems which are more robust and intelligent to the anti money laundering patterns. Over the coming years, these systems are only set to become more accurate and fast with the continuous innovations in the field of AI.

2. Chatbots: Chatbots are AI based automated chat systems which stimulate human chats without any human interventions. They work by identifying the context and emotions in the text chat by the human end user and respond to them with the most appropriate replay. It helps in maintaining customer relationship management at personal level. Human beings can become bored of answering the same type of questions asked by customers but these chatbots attend all the customers without any discrimination.

3. Algorithmic Trading: Plenty of hedge funds across the globe are using high end systems to deploy AI models which learn by taking input from several sources of variation in financial markets and sentiments about the entity to make investment decision on the fly 70% of trading today is actually carried out by automated AI systems.

4. Fraud Detection: This field needs more attention as banking activities are prone to many illegal activities. In the area of fund transfer, ATMs and data transferring channels are getting hacked by intelligent criminals. Falcon fraud assessment system, which is based on a neural network shell work to deployment of sophisticated deep learning based AI systems(Very well planned algorithms are used).

5. Customer Recommendations: Recommendation engines are a key contribution of AI in banking sector. It is based on using the data from the past about users and various offerings from a bank like credit card plans, investment strategies, funds etc. To make the most appropriate recommendation to the user based on their preferences and the users history. In the field of portfolio management this system is very useful.

6. Risk Management: Well customized products can be offered to clients by looking at historical data, CRISIL reports in order to avoid default risks.AI techniques will help to eliminate the human errors from handcrafted models. Suspicious behavior, suspicious emails can be tracked down to prevent customers’ interest.

Present Areas where AI has been Implemented Successfully in Banking Sector

SBI

- SBI has installed some scanning cameras in the branch and captures the facial expressions of the customers and immediately reports whether the customer is happy or sad. This is real time feedback.
- SBI has launched SIA as AI powered chat assistant that address customer enquiries instantly and helps them with everyday banking tasks. It can handle multiple questions at a time.

HDFC

- HDFC bank has developed an AI based chatbots, ‘ EVA’. Eva can assimilate knowledge from thousands of sources and provides simple answer in less than 0.4 seconds.
- HDFC also experimenting with in store robotic application that is IRA (In Store Robotic Assistant) appears to be research and development.

ICICI

- at ICICI bank, software robots have reduced the response time to customer by up to 60% and increased accuracy to 100% thereby improving the banks employees to focus more on value added and customer related functions.

Here software robots will capture and interpret information from systems and do processing and execute multiple activities.

Axis bank

Axis bank has installed Thought factory (TAT) that means previously an employee spend 15 minutes to open a savings account, now it takes 2- 3 minutes. To help reduce the turnaround time (TAT).

Future Areas where AI can be Implemented in Banking Sector

Statistics and predictions say that AI will become an important part of banking industry in future. According to capgemini a robot can perform jobs of 5 employees. Fintech report on India released in 2017 said that global investment in AI application touched \$5 billion in 2016.

In future, in order to increase accuracy of transactions reducing the costs. The AI can be used in banking industry another important activity that will become easy to perform with AI is data analytics.

Machine learning can effortlessly process a large amount of data smoothly in future. Customer's service can be enhanced accordingly.

But too much usage of AI in banking Industry can snatch the job opportunities from people and security risk also increases. The biggest challenge is the scarcity of trained human resources; because the existing workforce is not familiar with latest tools and application.

Suggestions

- Proactive efforts will be needed to stay ahead of attackers.
- Advanced technologies can be used to create better work opportunities and also can open the door for work force that can be implementing AI at the enterprise.
- Steps to process a transaction can be reduced in order to reduce the confusions in the minds of users.

Conclusion

Banking industry is the main source for economic activities and which influence the lifestyle of people of every country. As well as it also gets influenced by many factors such as inflation, deflations recessions, booms of the economy of country. It has been proved that the banking officials are always working in the stress environment with too much of workload and hence AI can be considered as a boon to them. Through the usage of AI in banking industry the efficiency of workers will increase to the maximum extent. It will bring the accuracy in the transactions helps in risk free activities through fraud detection techniques etc.

Many analysis also counters job defending technology- pessimists Gartner predicts that AI will not make human employment Obsolete, but it will create 2 million jobs in 2019. If this statement becomes true then the usage of AI will be the most welcoming technology in India.

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